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DETERMINATION OF VIBRATIONS CAUSED BY BLASTING PROCESSES IN OPEN PIT MINING AT MINING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. On the slope of an open pit, the rock mass has several joint structures, and blasting operations clearly affect its structure. Stability, therefore accurate prediction of blasting vibration is necessary to ensure slope stability. The explosion in this study The vibration signals observed at the blast site with different rock masses were used to study the attenuation characteristics. blast vibration through peak particle velocity, frequency characteristics, and energy distribution of the blast vibrational signals analyzed by time-frequency processing. The results showed that the fundamental oscillation frequency of the explosion vibration of dolomite was wider than that of shale, and these fundamental oscillation frequencies occurred at 50kHz. and 10 kHz for dolomite and shale, respectively, at a distance of 150 m from the blast site to the vibration monitoring point. With Increasing the distance from 50 m to 300 m, the fundamental vibration frequencies decreased to less than 8 Hz. With a growing joint degree, the rate of decay of the vibrational velocity and the energy decay of the detonation vibration increase, indicating that structural parameters of rocks (for example, the number of joints) have a significant effect on the attenuation law of explosion. vibration Furthermore, a modified equation has been developed that can be used to predict the field limit of Kohn. the number of joints in the rock mass by blasting vibration. Correlation factor for the same ground vibration readings It increased from 0.811 to 0.856 for the Nicholls-USBM equation and the modified equation, respectively. of blasting under +e Different rock masses of an opencast phosphorite deposit were used to test the modified equation. The results show that A modified equation can be used to predict blasting engineering in Badeng phosphorite mine and prediction accuracy is acceptable. With an error of +1,-1, we will be able to determine the frequency of oscillations of the explosion limit. I saw Otelbayev Azizbek blasting processes in the Tebin Bulak mine located in the territory of the Republic of

Karakalpakstan. We will be able to detect sound vibrations during the blasting process.

Keywords: Open pit blasting processes, underground stability, blast design and classification, explosion vibration, sound frequency.

Introduction

Environmental Protection Act and Geology and Mining Act requires the protection of the environment of the mineral extraction plant consequences of mining operations. This also applies to negative effects vibrations caused by blasting in people and building structures. Effective protection is possible only when the level of this effect is known, so it should be recorded. There is a thesis structured in this way has been and remains the leading principle of research It was carried out in mine blasting and environmental laboratory Protection. As a result of these works, transfer procedures are in place preventive measures by open-pit mines in order to minimize the impact exploding surrounding objects. An important element of this the activity is to monitor vibrations in the source structures knowledge for excavation supervisors and blasting engineers works, thereby contributing to raising the awareness of responsible persons. However, only a few studies have been conducted in the open pit is carried out in connection with the propagation of the vibration wave properties of structural planes. Research on vibration the blast effect described the transmission and reflection of the stress wave at the surface of the structure using theoretical analysis and focusing primarily on the effect of amplitude attenuation of structures on the stress wave. therefore, studies on the effects of stone media on detonation vibration damping and accurate analysis influence of rock formations on the distribution of vibration damping in the blasting technique is worth further investigation. Over the past few decades, it has become increasingly complex approaches such as finite element method and artificial neural networks have been used to predict burst oscillations. Many researchers have tried successfully processing and analysis of unstable random burst vibration signals using signal time-frequency analysis. There are studies the effect of distance from the explosion was also studied the center of the energy distribution of the frequency range of the explosion vibration signals and signal time-frequency analysis are available becomes an efficient method of energy research distribution characteristics of the explosion vibration signal under rock mass joints. Based on the time frequency results characteristics of explosion signals, study of factors exposure to detonation vibration, setting regression the formula describing the detonation vibration and the analysis of the signal time

frequency are effective and important methods explosive vibration hazard study. Ammonium nitrate-fuel oil and without electricity detonators were used for blasting excavations. The typical depth and diameter of the blast holes is 11 m and 130 mm, respectively, resulting in a blasting pattern 4 m load and 5 m distance. In-hole delay detonators work at a speed of 400 ms. A starting pattern has been produced surface using calculations with a delay of 25 ms. An example is the location of the starting grid and drill holes. Picture 1 shows.

Picture 1. location of drill holes.

Vibration during mine blasting observation points and the explosion area are located in the same place it is necessary to calculate the distance from the height to the boundary area. Distances between observation points and blasting area 50, 100, 150 and 200 m. Each observation point is equipped with a vibration sensor. The sensor must be glued to the surface undamaged stone with plaster, and monitoring position points must be adjusted accordingly to ensure accuracy from measurements. Distance and location coordinates were the place. As shown in Picture 2, it is determined using GPS.

Picture 2. Vibration sensor and GPS

It is known that underground safety and stability Shafts, sidewalls/pillars, dams, etc., located close to working open pits are often at risk of explosion. induced

vibrations. Mine operators try to break up the rock better, even if blasting requires more consumption explosives per ton of mineral produced, reducing loading, hauling and crushing costs due to improved fragmentation. minerals. These explosions cause seismic disturbances twisting can damage and potentially impact the support system stability of roof and side walls / pillars of galleries in underground mines. This can cause cracks to open in the layers, making them unstable. In addition, there is a possibility of falling inside neighboring works. Seismic disturbances caused by blasting depends on the total explosive energy released during detonation and the proximity of the underground workings to the open pit. There are several examples of underground mines working near a working open pit mine. In this case operations, ground vibrations caused by explosions can be a potential reason for the instability of Neighboring underground mines and can be dangerous. Such In some mines there is a situation where open and underground mines are working with 70 m separation and a final separation of only 50-60 m is planned. Explosions Hanging wall, legs are carried out on different benches wall and ore machines of an open pit mine. For one delay, explosive weight, travel distance and properties of the conducting media (elastic modulus and density) have a significant effect on the vibration characteristics generated in underground structures by a nearby explosion.

Conclusions

Explosion-induced vibration data from the pyrotechnics and the electronic launch system were analyzed separately. The results showed that the electronic starting system. The vibration level is 10-15% lower than the pyrotechnic launch system in underground holes. If recommended Blasting in an open pit should be done at 100m or closer (i.e. up to 60 m from underground openings) should be initiated with electronic detonators to increase blasting safety adjacent underground holes. Comparative analyzes of peak particle velocities are reported caused by open blasting and in underground holes shows that the vibration recorded in underground holes was much lower than that recorded on the surface distances of the same scale. Along with the geometric spread, it was found that underground spaces play an important role attenuation of ground vibrations. Detonation vibration reduction in a was up to 43,3% compared to those recorded on the surface scaled distance was 27. High frequency ground vibration data recorded in underground holes, and on the surface low frequency ground vibration data observed due to open pit blasting. In this study, burst vibration signals were observed open pit dolomite and shale blasting sites

phosphorite mine. Also, the laws of attenuation on blasting vibration signals in rock masses that have characteristics were analyzed using a wave packet time frequency analysis method. Based on the results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

* Detonation vibration reduction coefficient is indicated exact relationship with the rock mass. Weakening coefficient of law for blast shock waves, k and n had and in dolomite and open pit shale blasting sites, in line.

*Time-frequency analysis of wavelet packets is basically and the spectra of are composed of low frequencies blast vibration signals mainly consist of the following low frequencies, with the main vibrational frequency in the range of 0-50 Hz. the fundamental vibrational frequency decreases with increasing distance observation points.

* The degree of joint development of rocks affected the decay rate of PM, and when PM attenuation is high rocks have a large number of joints. New relationships were developed to improve the prediction of PM in different rock masses open pit, taking into account the degree of development and number of joints in the rock mass.

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